
GLOBAL DIGITAL ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT AND IT SERVICES EXPORT

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Abstract.

One of the priorities of the development of the world economy at the beginning of the 21st century is the formation of a digital economy. The digital economy offers countries in transition a wide range of opportunities in terms of value creation and benefits from the digital economy. The digital economy is developing based on the collection, use and analysis of very large amounts of information.

Key words.

digital economy, economy, transformation, export, information communication technologies, IT export.

Introduction

As it is known, it is important to further stabilize our society and thereby further strengthen the position of our country in the world community by focusing on innovative activities. Therefore, in our country, large-scale work aimed at increasing the efficiency of scientific research activities, strengthening the role of economic sciences in social and economic development and democratic renewal of the country is being carried out. At the moment, it is time to further develop the effective application of innovative technologies and developments that serve to increase the power of our state and improve the well-being of our people.

In 1992, the volume of information flow in the world was 100 gigabytes (GB) per day, and by 2017, this indicator was equal to 45 thousand GB. According to forecasts, the size of IP graphics is expected to reach 150 thousand gb per second.

Also, our president Sh. Mirziyoev said, "Of course, we know very well that the formation of the digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, a lot of money and labor resources. However, no matter how hard it is, if we don't start today, when will we?! Tomorrow will be too late. Therefore, active transition to the

digital economy will be one of our top priorities in the next 5 years . These thoughts indicate the relevance of the digital economy in the current economy.

The main part

The impact of the digital economy on the world economy is occurring in two directions:

First, a new value-added chain is created due to monetization in the process of turning the collected data into digital intelligence and using it for commercial purposes.

The second direction is a digital platform, which is based on the data collected by business models and leads to changes in the sectors operating in the economy.

According to the analysis, seven of the eight largest companies by market capitalization in the world are effectively using business model platforms. In the world, the gap between countries with weak internet connections and countries with very high levels of digitalization is becoming sharper. The leading place in the geography of the world's digital economy is occupied by the United States and China. They account for 75% of the world's patents related to blockchain technology, 52% of internet spending, 75% of the created global technology market (Cloud system), and 90% of the market capitalization of the world's 70 largest digital platforms.

The following important advantages and advantages of the digital economy over the traditional economy can be listed:

- the balance between the efficiency of the state administration policy and the quality of execution of public services is ensured;
- large-scale structural changes will occur in industries with high added value by transferring the value creation chain from one place to another in the economy;
- serves to accelerate the development of innovation and the introduction of its results into production;
- it is possible to direct economic sectors to a specific result through targeted programming;
- labor productivity is increased several times by digitalization of production processes;
- return of investments accelerates due to the increase in the scope and efficiency of use of networks and equipment;
- execution of complex financial operations becomes simpler, information exchange takes place in seconds;

- due to the expansion of the virtual scope, the quality of services provided to the population will increase and become simpler;
- due to the wide use of intellectual potential, material expenses will decrease and the level of profitability will increase;
- it will be possible to centrally manage the operations of sellers (Multi-Vendor) operating in online stores on the electronic platform (online e-commerce market place).

The development of the digital economy creates the basis for the emergence of a large number of new economic opportunities. Digital data is transforming the value chain in the economy, opening up new opportunities for increasing added value and causing profound structural changes. To increase the creation of added value and profit of the digital economy impact through a number of indicators (including labor productivity, amount of value added, employment, income and sales) can be analyzed.

The following factors influence the development of the digital economy:

- the absence of a universally recognized single tariff for the digital economy;
- lack of reliable statistical data necessary for calculating the digital economy in developing and transition economy countries;
- telecommunication infrastructure digital of interruptions preserved remaining ;
- society by digital to the documents and to services has been distrust level and them state bodies, judicial offices by acceptance to be done insecurity;
- digital technologies apply in the field high qualified of experts absence, including their from the country gone stay with dependence;
- digital technologies to apply directed projects state by of financing inefficiency, transparent and enough in volume that it is not, and of the country regions development in the section from the budget except savings funds attraction to reach encourage mechanism absence;
- in the state available statistics _ system and of resources different variety and dispersion.

XXI century in their heads digital of the economy the world in GDP share to various calculations according to, 4.5-15.5 percent organize is doing.

Result

Analyzes according to the world information and communication technologies (ICT) sector created added 40.0 percent of the value is US and China contribution

right The number of people employed in the ICT sector in the world in 2010 34 million per year. 39 million per person in 2015. to the person did _ Among them, 38 percent of them are computer services busy in the field or of the world's busy people common 1.8-2.0 percent of the number of AQT sector contribution right

will come Computer services industry the world in the economy the only one as a sector of the world all in the regions stable paces with is developing. Even the — Covid-19 pandemic conditions too fast paces with developed and economic in terms of the most high income which brings promising from networks to one became Analyzes — Covid- 19 pandemic conditions Internet network in USA through weekly movies to see volume 32 percent, short metered videos vision to 36 percent and game platforms traffics volume by 75 percent increased. In the first quarter of 2020 Americans to video games spent costs 11 bln. to doll increased.

XXI century in their heads of ICT services in the world export volume common of services for export relatively fast paces with is developing. This situation the world economy increasingly digitized that it is going again proves once. Including 2018 digital technologies using shown services of export volume is 2.9 trn. doll. organize in the world services to 50 percent of its exports equal to it happened Although this the indicator increased 3 times in 2005-2018. Digital platforms the world in the economy increasingly large importance occupation reached is going in 2017 digital platforms based on activity pointer market capitalization is 100 mln. from doll more than has been of companies gross worth 7 trillion. US dollars organize did and this indicator for 2015 compared to 67 percent increased. in the world some global digital platforms known in segments the world in the market strong to positions have it happened For example, in the world 90 percent of the internet search systems to Google belongs to is considered —Facebook to the company while the world social networks 2/3 of the market right will come and his platform in the world social networks from 90 percent more than countries leader place catch, popular is considered

Amazon accounts for 40 % of global retail online sales branches through done is increased. The coronavirus pandemic conditions

Amazon company of USA income sharp increased and Online shopping giant a lot numerous new work places created, to employees payable work right size increased. of Amazon success his Founder Geoffrey Bezos is born in 2020 of the planet the status of the richest man again to occupy once reason it happened

Above names given digital the giants in the market leader role increase the following factors with is defined as:

□ little girl effect (i.e from the platform users number increase his value to growth take arrived);

□ of platforms information search, control to do and analysis to do ability with depends.

Summary

Digital of the economy development national economies competitiveness above , below relative advantages reach enable gives : first , national of the economy stable in paces growth provides . Economical to grow provide the following levers through done is increased:

□ inclusive- social to processes maximum in quantity citizens attraction reach;

□ innovation development and his efficiency increaseю

Above measures done increase national in economics trade, capital and workforce sizes _ and their mobility increase with one in line, healthy competition environment to increase take will come

Second, digital of the economy development work the market transform enable gives _ This transformation is a complex character have will be and of the economy traditional networks slowly slowly digital to the economy attraction reach through done is increased.

Global studies shows digital the economy from development removable effect positive to the character have will be For example, the McKinsey company to calculations according to, in the field of ICT created one work place in general 2-4 jobs in the economy places opening encourages. PWC Company to calculations according to the economy to 10 percent of digitization increase unemployment level of 0.84 percent to decrease take will come The last 15 years during in France conducted deep analyses as shown, work places digitization because of from work released 500 thousand work place in the country additional 1.2 mln. work places create enable gaveю

The economy digitization transition countries of the economy network and sectors economic and social dividends to increase take will come Digital the economy to form acceleration for the following measures done increase to the goal according to is :

□ transition economy countries until 2030 has been to the period intended digital the economy development strategy acceptance to do;

□ digital the economy legal and institutional the basics regularly by improving to go;

□ digital economy infrastructure development for investments attraction reach mechanism create and more development it is necessary.

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